

Effects of Probability Distribution Characteristics of Snow Load on Relationships between Load Factors and Reliability Indexes of Cylindrical Lattice Shell Roofs with Various Substructure Stiffnesses

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Abstract

There have been no studies on the reliability indexes of cylindrical lattice shell roofs that focus on the effects of substructure stiffness or on the probabilistic characteristics of snow load. This paper investigates the relationships between the reliability index and the snow load factor for cylindrical lattice shell roofs with various substructure stiffnesses under snow loading. The bending stiffness of the substructure is determined on the basis of a model designed in the elastic range for dead loads and seismic force with the base shear coefficient. For a parametric study, the bending stiffness of the substructure is proportioned. The snow loads have the characteristics of a probability distribution of snow depth from the average value and standard deviation results of the 100-year return period snow depth in Japan. All random variables are assumed to follow a log-normal distribution and to be independent of each other. The reliability indexes are calculated using AFOSM method considering different snow depth for a parametric study.

Keywords: Cylindrical Lattice Shell Roof, Stiffness of Supporting Substructure, Load Factor, Characteristics of Probability Distribution, 100-year Return Period Snow Depth, Reliability Index

1. Introduction

The allowable stress design used in Japan has demerits that we cannot accurately evaluate the ultimate strength of members for example (Suzuki [1]). In developed countries in the West, the limit state design method based on the reliability theory is applied (Morisaki et al [2]).

In regards to the ultimate limit state design of steel structures, there are Recommendation for Limit State Design of Steel Structures, published by Architectural Institute of Japan, and Load & Resistance Factor Design (LRFD) by American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC), which are applied for member strength. However, the buckling of a lattice shell is a phenomenon affecting a total collapse of a structure, so the value of reliability index assumed in design is considered to be different from the one of members. The study on reliability analysis of free from lattice shells have different buckling behavior. Therefore, it is important to accumulate the results by reliability analysis of cylindrical lattice shells which are not taken as an object of previous studies.

In particular, the boundary conditions of the roof structure play a critical role in determining the fundamental load transfer characteristics and buckling behavior, similar to the form and configuration of lattice shells. For investigations of the buckling behavior of lattice shells with substructures, when only the roof structure is analyzed, the boundary conditions must be appropriately defined, taking into

account factors such as the stiffness and weight of the substructure, as well as the method of connection between the roof structure and the substructure. Previous studies by Kato et al [3] and Kumagai et al [4] on the reliability indices of cylindrical lattice shells roof have primarily considered pin supports or roller supports, for example. However, there is a paucity of research focusing on the reliability indices influenced by the stiffness of the substructure. Similarly, while studies have evaluated the buckling strength of cylindrical lattice shell roofs with pin or roller supports, the effects of substructure stiffness on buckling strength and behavior remain unexplored.

On the other hand, it is well known that snow load significantly influence the design of steel structures with small dead load per unit area by Ishikawa et al [5]. In the design of lattice shells, consideration of snow load is essential. The magnitude of the expected snow load varies greatly depending on the surrounding topography and climatic conditions. In Recommendations for Loads on Buildings(AIJ [6]) in Japan, the expected snow depth at each location over the 100-year return period is calculated using a regression line. Since the average of the snow depth over the 100-year return period and the average and standard deviation of the observed annual maximum snow depth vary widely from location to location, the stochastic characteristics of the 100-year maximum snow depth is also expected to vary from location to location. Consequently, it is essential to accumulate information on the relationship between load factors of buckling loads and reliability indices when various probabilistic characteristics of snow loads are considered. However, studies focusing on the reliability indices of lattice shells under probabilistic snow load characteristics are not available.

Therefore, this study conducts a reliability analysis of cylindrical lattice shell roofs with varying substructure stiffness under different probabilistic characteristics of snow loads. The relationship between load factors of buckling loads and reliability indexes is elucidated. To clarify the effects of substructure stiffness and boundary condition differences on this relationship, models with varying substructure stiffness and models of roof structures alone with pin or pin-roller supports along the periphery are examined and compared. The coefficients used in the buckling strength calculation formulae for performance functions are analyzed for their dependence on substructure stiffness, and new formulations are proposed. In the reliability analysis, the primary random variable is snow depth. The study examines how differences in the average and standard deviation of snow depth influence the relationship between reliability indices and load factors.

2. Analyzed models and numerical analysis methods of cylindrical lattice shell roofs

Analysis model is shown in Fig.1. Member properties are shown in Table 1. Analyzed models are cylindrical lattice shell roofs which have a comparable span of the same as school gymnasium.

Young's modulus E is 206000N/mm² for all members.

Fig. 1: Analysis model
(Cylindrical lattice shell roof)

Table 1: Member properties

		Diameter D [cm]	Thickness t [cm]	Sectional area A [cm ²]	Geometrical moment of inertia I [cm ⁴]	Slenderness ratio λ	
Roof Structure	Lattice member	$\lambda \approx 45$	25.40	0.45, 0.80	35.27, 61.83	2746, 4682	42.32, 42.79
		$\lambda \approx 60$	19.07	0.70, 1.20	40.40, 67.37	1707, 2701	57.29, 58.80
		$\lambda \approx 75$	16.52	0.90, 1.50	44.16, 70.78	1351, 2016	67.49, 69.77
	Arch of gable direction	50.80	1.00	156.5	48520	17.83	
	Beam of gable direction	40.64	1.10	136.6	26720	19.91	
	Beam of longitudinal direction	40.64	0.80	100.1	19870	28.39	
Substructure	Post	19.07	0.82	23.46	1022.7	21.96	
	Column	Stiffness 0.1x	21.03	2.07	123.2	5600	88.98
		Stiffness 1.0x	60.96	0.65	123.2	56000	28.14
		Stiffness 5.0x	135.2	0.29	123.2	280002	12.58
		Stiffness 10x	190.9	0.21	123.2	560005	8.90
	Stiffness 100x	603.2	0.06	123.2	5600047	2.81	
Beam of gable direction	60.96	0.75	141.9	64298	-		
Beam of longitudinal direction	60.96	1.00	188.4	84677	21.20		

The bending stiffness of the substructure is based on a model designed in the elastic range for dead loads and seismic forces with the base shear coefficient $C_0=0.3$. The bending stiffness of the substructure is proportioned to the model above by 1.0x, 5.0x and 10x. Additionally, buckling analysis is conducted for models with substructure stiffness magnifications of 0.1x and 100x to analyze the impact of various

stiffness values on the structure. In this case, the cross-sectional area and Young's modulus of the member remain unchanged.

For the substructure-inclusive model, the boundary condition is fixed at the column base, and the roof and substructure are connected with pin joints around the perimeter. For roof-only models, the boundary conditions are set as pin support or pin-roller support at peripheral nodes, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The half open angle of shell roofs θ is 30 degrees, and member slenderness ratios λ are set to 45, 60, and 75. The shape of initial imperfection considered is the first or second buckling mode, and the geometrical imperfection w_{i0} is 20% of the equivalent shell thickness t_{eq} . Numerical analyses include linear eigenvalue analysis and static elastic or elastoplastic buckling analysis considering geometric nonlinearity. Each lattice member is divided into two elements for the analysis to account for member buckling. Roof-only models are named R30- $\lambda(45, 60, 75)$ -Boundary Conditions (pin, pinrol), while models with substructures are named F30- $\lambda(45, 60, 75)$ -Substructure Stiffness Ratio (0.1, 1, 5, 10, 100).

Fig. 2: The boundary condition (Roof-only models)

3. Formulation of the Buckling Strength Calculation Method

3.1. Overview of Buckling Strength Calculation Formulation

In reliability analysis, it is necessary to derive a buckling load calculation formula that incorporates the variability of probabilistic variables to evaluate the strength of lattice shells. The buckling load P_{cr} of cylindrical lattice shells under uniform snow load is calculated based on the equations proposed in AIJ Recommendation for Design of Latticed Shell Roof Structures (AIJ [7]) and the previous study by Kato et al [8]. The relationship between the substructure stiffness ratio and various coefficients in the buckling load formula is analyzed and formulated.

In this study, the substructure stiffness is defined as the bending stiffness K_C of the column, modeled as a cantilever beam:

$$K_C = \frac{3EI}{L^3} \quad (1)$$

where, E is the Young's modulus, I is geometrical moment of inertia of the column. the column height is $L = 6.0\text{m}$.

The structural characteristics of cylindrical lattice shells with substructures are influenced not only by substructure stiffness but also by the out-of-plane stiffness of the roof structure. The roof's out-of-plane stiffness is primarily affected by the half open angle θ and the member slenderness ratio λ . Assuming the cylindrical surface is slightly flattened, the out-of-plane stiffness is examined as the stiffness in the vertical load-displacement relationship. Based on the previous study by Kumagai et al [4], the vertical stiffness of pin-roller supported roof structures increases quadratically with θ and decreases quadratically with λ . Thus, the vertical stiffness is assumed to be proportional to $(\theta/\lambda)^2$, as shown in Fig 3. These are correspondences. Therefore, the formulation incorporates $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$, as a variable to account for the effects of both substructure stiffness and roof's out-of-plane stiffness. Table 2 lists the values of K_C and $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$, for each model. For roof-only models, K_C is assumed to be infinity for pin supports and 1.0 for pin-roller supports.

Fig. 3: $(\theta/\lambda)^2$ and the vertical stiffness of the roof surface by Kumagai et al [4]

Table 2: The values of K_C and $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$

The boundary condition/ The substructure stiffness	$K_C(=3EI/L^3)$ [N/m]	$\lambda=45$	$\lambda=60$	$\lambda=75$
		$K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$ [N/m]		
pin-support	∞	∞	∞	∞
100x	1.60×10^8	21356	11590	8395
10x	1.60×10^7	2136	1159	840
5.0x	8.01×10^6	1068	580	420
1.0x	1.60×10^6	214	116	84
0.1x	1.60×10^5	21	12	8
pin · roller-support	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

3.2. Buckling resistance formula considering the effect of substructure stiffness

In this subsection, the plastic load P_{SQ} , the linear buckling load P_{cr}^{lin} , the knockdown factor α_0 , the generalized slenderness ratio Λ_S , and the elasto-plastic buckling load P_{cr} are derived and valued.

The elasto-plastic buckling load P_{cr} calculated by the following modified Dunkerley's equation using the generalized slenderness ratio Λ_S and the plastic load P_{SQ} .

$$P_{cr} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Lambda_S^4 + 4 + \Lambda_S^2}} \cdot P_{SQ} \quad (2)$$

The generalized slenderness ratio Λ_S is given as the form:

$$\Lambda_S = \sqrt{\frac{P_{SQ}}{\alpha_0 \cdot P_{cr}^{lin}}} \quad (3)$$

where the plastic load P_{SQ} is calculated by Eq. (4),

$$P_{SQ} = \gamma_m \cdot 4A\sigma_y \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot \theta_0 \quad (4)$$

where A , σ_y , φ , and θ_0 denote the sectional area of members yield stress of steel members, the angle between a stringer and a diagonal member shown in Fig. 4, and subtended half angle of members. An adjustment factor γ_m is calculated by Eq. (5).

$$\gamma_m = \frac{P_{SQ(FEM)}}{4A\sigma_y \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot \theta_0} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 4: Detail of mesh pattern of roof

where $P_{SQ(FEM)}$ is the plastic load predicted by the finite element method.

where P_{cr}^{lin} denote the linear buckling load of cylindrical lattice shells under vertical loads. The linear buckling load of cylindrical lattice shells under vertical loads P_{cr}^{lin} is calculated by Eq. (6).

$$P_{cr}^{lin} = \omega^{lin} \cdot p_0 \cdot A_{node} \quad (6)$$

where p_0 is the linear buckling load when the boundary condition is simply supported, A_{node} is the influence area of the load at each node, ω^{lin} is a surcharge coefficient.

The relationship of the adjustment factor γ_m , the surcharge coefficient ω^{lin} , and the knockdown factor α_0 with $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$, respectively, is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: The relationships between adjustment factor γ_m , surcharge coefficient ω^{lin} , and knockdown factor α_0 and $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$

For γ_m and ω^{lin} according to the relationship with $K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2$, an approximate formulas Eqs. (7) and (8) are shown by the least-squares method.

$$\begin{cases} \gamma_m = 0.22 & (K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2 \leq 25.6) \\ \gamma_m = 0.163 \cdot \log_{10}[K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2] - 0.107 & (25.6 \leq K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2 \leq 27036) \\ \gamma_m = 0.71 & (27036 < K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{cases} \omega^{lin} = 1.39 & (K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2 \leq 15.6) \\ \omega^{lin} = 0.115 \cdot \log_{10}[K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2] + 1.25 & (15.6 \leq K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2 \leq 28252) \\ \omega^{lin} = 1.76 & (28252 < K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In addition, since the value of α_0 for the 0.1x model is below the value for the pin-roller support and the value for the 100x model is above the value for the pin support, there is no continuity between the roof-only models and the models with the substructure. Therefore, based on the results of the finite element method, α_0 is approximated by the following equations for the model with substructure only: $w_{io}/t_{eq}=0.0, 0.2$, respectively.

$$w_{io}/t_{eq} = 0.0: \alpha_0 = 0.0719 \cdot \log_{10}[K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2] + 0.585 \text{ and } \alpha_0 \leq 1.0 \quad (9)$$

$$w_{io}/t_{eq} = 0.2: \alpha_0 = 0.0503 \cdot \log_{10}[K_C(\theta/\lambda)^2] + 0.537 \text{ and } \alpha_0 \leq 1.0 \quad (10)$$

Since P_{cr} calculated from the above is an approximate formula, the elasto-plastic buckling load $P_{cr(FEM)}$ obtained from the finite element method is used to calculate the buckling load ratio ω obtained from the following equation, which is used in the reliability analysis.

$$\omega = P_{cr(FEM)}/P_{cr} \quad (11)$$

4. Characteristics of the probability of snow depth

In the reliability analysis of this study, the primary probabilistic variable is the snow depth h_s . The relationship between the reliability index and the load factor is analyzed by varying the average and standard deviation of the snow depth. To determine the probabilistic characteristics of the snow depth, the average value $\mu_{S_{p100}}$ and standard deviation $\sigma_{S_{p100}}$ of the expected 100-year maximum snow depth are calculated using the methodology in the previous study by Mori and Maruyama [9]. It is assumed that the annual maximum snow depth S_{p1} and the 100-year maximum snow depth follow a log-normal distribution. The probability distribution function of the n -year maximum snow depth S_{pn} , when S_{p1} is a log-normal random variable, is given by Eq. (12), and its average value $\mu_{S_{pn}}$ and coefficient of variation $\nu_{S_{pn}}$ are approximated by Eqs. (13) and (14):

$$F_{S_{pn}}(x) = \Phi \left(\frac{\ln x - \mu_{\ln S_{p1}}}{\sigma_{\ln S_{p1}}} \right)^n \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_{S_{pn}} = \mu_{S_{p1}} \left\{ 1.0 + 1.1v_{S_{p1}} - 3.0v_{S_{p1}}^2 + \left(-0.045 + 0.56v_{S_{p1}} + v_{S_{p1}}^2 \right) \ln(n) \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$v_{S_{pn}} = v_{S_{p1}} \cdot [0.865 - 0.138 \cdot \ln(n) + 0.0098 \cdot \{\ln(n)\}^2] \quad (14)$$

where, $\mu_{S_{p1}}$ and $\sigma_{\ln S_{p1}}$ represent the average and standard deviation of $\ln(S_{p1})$, and $v_{S_{p1}}$ is the coefficient of variation of S_{p1} . The values of $\mu_{S_{p1}}$ and $\sigma_{\ln S_{p1}}$ for annual maximum snow depths are obtained from observation data at meteorological stations across Japan, as documented in the previous study by Ishikawa et al [5]. The computed values of $\mu_{S_{p100}}$, $\sigma_{S_{p100}}$, and $v_{S_{p100}}$ are shown in Fig. 6. Based on these results, the probabilistic characteristics of h_s for this study are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 6 : Expected snow depth for 100-year return period in Japan

Table 3: Characteristics of probability distribution of snow depth h_s

Average[m]	Standard deviation[m]	Coefficients of variation	Mode[m]	Type of distribution
0.3	0.2	0.67	0.28	Log Normal
	0.1	0.20	0.49	
	0.2	0.40	0.47	
0.5	0.3	0.60	0.44	
	0.2	0.20	0.94	
1.0	0.2	0.10	1.89	

5. Reliability analysis

5.1. Calculation of loads

The loads considered in the reliability analysis include dead loads and uniformly distributed snow loads. The nominal snow load $S_{(n)}$ per unit area and the unit weight of snow $\rho_{S(n)}$ are calculated using Eqs. (15) and (16) from the previous study by Ishikawa et al [5]:

$$S_{(n)} = \rho_{S(n)} \cdot h_{S(n)} \quad (15)$$

$$\rho_{S(n)} = 0.72 \sqrt{h_s/h_{ref}} + 2.32 \quad (16)$$

where h_s represents the snow depth, and h_{ref} is the reference snow depth, which is 1.0m. Subscript (n) indicates nominal values. The nominal values of dead and snow loads used in the reliability analysis are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Details of loads targeted in reliability analysis

Snow load				Dead load
$h_{s(n)}$ [m]	$\rho_{s(n)}$ [kN/m ³]	$\rho_{s(n)}h_{s(n)}$ [kN/m ²]	$\rho_{s(n)}h_{s(n)}A_{node}$ [kN]	P_{DL} [kN]
0.3	2.71	0.81	10.2	12.7 ($\lambda=45$)
0.5	2.83	1.41	17.8	12.7 ($\lambda=60$)
1.0	3.04	3.04	38.2	12.6 ($\lambda=75$)
2.0	3.34	6.68	83.9	

5.2. Performance Function and Failure Probability

For the cylindrical lattice shell roof, the reliability of buckling against snow loads is evaluated. AFOSM (Advanced First-Order Second-Moment) method (Hoshino and Ishii [10]) is applied to the reliability analysis. The performance function Z used to calculate the failure probability P_{fl} is given by Eq. (17):

$$Z = \omega \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Lambda_S^4 + 4 + \Lambda_S^2}} \cdot \gamma_m \cdot 4A\sigma_y \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot \theta_0 - P_{DL} - A_{node} \cdot \rho_{S(n)} \cdot h_{S(n)} \quad (17)$$

where P_{DL} is the dead load at the center point on roof. The calculated values of P_{cr} and ω for the $\lambda = 60$ model are shown in Table 5.

Table5: The values of P_{cr} and ω ($\lambda = 60$)

λ	The boundary condition/ The substructure stiffness	w_0/t_{eq}	P_{cr} [kN]	$P_{cr(FEM)}$ [kN]	ω
60	pin-support	0.0	45.1	51.8	1.15
		0.2	38.3	42.2	1.10
	10x	0.0	37.0	45.9	1.24
		0.2	33.3	40.0	1.20
	5.0x	0.0	34.4	41.0	1.19
		0.2	31.1	36.7	1.18
	1.0x	0.0	28.3	34.0	1.20
		0.2	25.9	30.7	1.19
	pin · roller-support	0.0	22.0	30.5	1.39
		0.2	20.3	26.9	1.33

The failure probability P_{fl} is defined as Eq. (18):

$$P_{fl} = Prob(Z \leq 0) \quad (18)$$

The reliability index β is obtained by AFOSM method.

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_Z}{\sigma_Z} \quad (19)$$

where μ_Z and σ_Z denote the average and standard deviation, respectively, of the performance function Z at a failure point obtained.

Therefore, the failure probability P_{fl} is calculated as Eq. (20):

$$P_{fl} = 1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\mu_Z}{\sigma_Z}\right) \quad (20)$$

where Φ denotes a normal Gaussian cumulative distribution function.

The properties of probabilistic variables applied to the reliability analysis are listed in Table 6. For all probabilistic variables, the averages are equal to the nominal values. The coefficients of variation for each probabilistic variable are assumed based on Recommendations for Loads on Buildings (AIJ [6]) in Japan and the study by Kato [3]. In this paper, the log normal distribution is adopted as the one of snow loads. It turned out that the distribution of snow fall is the log normal distribution by the study by Maeda [11] while some studies have applied the Gumbel distribution. Each probabilistic variable is independent in this paper.

Table 6: Properties of probabilistic variables considered in reliability analyses

The ramdam variables	Average	Coefficients of variation	Nominal value	Type of distribution
σ_y [N/mm ²]	300	0.081	300	Log Normal
θ_0 [rad]	0.044	0.001	0.044	
A [cm ²]	A in Table1	0.03	A in Table1	
λ	λ in Table1	0.04	λ in Table1	
E [N/mm ²]	206000	0.087	206000	
ω	ω in Table5	0.001	ω in Table5	
h_s [m]	h_s in Table3	h_s in Table3	h_s in Table3	

5.3. Results of reliability analysis

The results of the reliability analysis are shown. The relationship between the reliability index β and the failure probability P_{ft} is shown in Table 7. For example, in case of $\beta=3.0$, 1.35 structures per 1000 structures collapse.

Table 7: The relationships between reliability index β and failure probability P_{ft}

β	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0
P_{ft}	6.681 %	2.275 %	0.621 %	0.135 %	0.0233 %	0.00317 %

The reliability analysis results for the average of buckling load $P_{cr(c)}$ and reliability index β are presented in Table 8. A dash ("-") in the table indicates that the analysis could not converge due to a low value of β . From Table 8, it is observed that for the same probabilistic characteristics of h_s , the values of $P_{cr(c)}$ and β increase as the member slenderness ratio λ decreases and the substructure stiffness increases. For the same model, β increases as the standard deviation $\sigma_{(h_s)}$ of snow depth decreases, indicating that smaller variations in load lead to a lower failure probability.

Fig. 7 shows $P_{cr(c)}$ when targeting $\beta = 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0$ respectively. $P_{cr(c)}$ tends to be slightly larger in models with substructure than in roof only models. This may be due to the fact that models with substructure takes into account the variability of random variables in the values of ω^{lin} , γ_m , and α_0 , while roof only models take them as deterministic values. However, in general, when the characteristics of h_s are the same, the same target value of β requires the same level of $P_{cr(c)}$, regardless of the model, and is strongly affected by the variability of h_s .

Table 8: Average of buckling load $P_{cr(c)}$ and reliability index β by reliability analysis

Model name	w_o/t_{eq}	$P_{cr(c)}$ [kN]	Reliability index β							
			$\mu(h_s):0.3m$		$\mu(h_s):0.5m$		$\mu(h_s):1.0m$		$\mu(h_s):2.0m$	
			$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.1m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.3m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$	$\sigma(h_s):0.2m$
			$v(h_s):0.67$	$v(h_s):0.2$	$v(h_s):0.4$	$v(h_s):0.6$	$v(h_s):0.2$	$v(h_s):0.1$		
R30-60-pin	0.0	51.8	2.29	3.28	1.97	1.53	0.17	-	-	
	0.2	42.2	1.86	2.07	1.32	1.08	-	-		
F30-60-10	0.0	46.0	2.04	2.57	1.59	1.27	-	-		
	0.2	40.1	1.75	1.75	1.15	0.95	-	-		
F30-60-5	0.0	41.1	1.81	1.91	1.23	1.01	-	-		
	0.2	36.7	1.55	1.22	0.84	0.74	-	-		
F30-60-1	0.0	34.1	1.38	0.77	0.58	0.56	-	-		
	0.2	30.8	1.13	0.12	0.20	0.28	-	-		
R30-60-pinrol	0.0	30.5	1.12	0.06	0.17	0.26	-	-		
	0.2	26.9	0.78	-	-	-	-	-		

Fig. 7: The relationships between reliability index β and average of buckling load $P_{cr(c)}$

6. Calculation of load factors

This chapter presents the calculation of load factors based on the results of the reliability analysis.

The snow load factor is calculated as Eq. (21):

$$\gamma_s = \frac{p_{v0(n)} - \gamma_d \cdot p_{d0(n)}}{\rho_s h_{s(n)}} \quad (21)$$

where γ_d is the load factor of dead load. The value of γ_d is 1.1 in this study. $p_{d0(n)}$ is dead load. $p_{v0(n)}$ is the ultimate design load per unit area applied to a cylindrical lattice shell, which is designed assuming a yield stress $\sigma_y = 235 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and an amplitude of geometrical initial imperfection $w_{i0}/t_{eq} = 0.2$. $p_{v0(n)}$ is calculated as Eqs. (22) and (23):

$$\alpha_{cr(FEM)} = \frac{P_{cr(FEM)}(235,0.2)}{P_{cr(FEM)}(300,w_{i0}/t_{eq})} \quad (22)$$

$$p_{v0(n)} = \frac{(\alpha_{cr(FEM)} \cdot P_{cr(c)})}{A_{node}} \quad (23)$$

The global load factor γ_n for the dead load $p_{d0(n)}$ and the snow load $S_{(n)}$ is defined as the following Eq. (24).

$$\gamma_n = \frac{\gamma_d \cdot p_{d0(n)} + \gamma_S \cdot \rho_S h_{S(n)}}{p_{d0(n)} + \rho_S h_{S(n)}} \quad (24)$$

The relationship between γ_S and the probability of failure $\ln(P_{fl})$ at $\mu(h_S)=0.5m$ and the relationships between γ_n and the reliability index β are shown in Fig. 8. The value of the load factor required to satisfy a given β is larger for smaller substructure stiffness when the probability characteristics of snow depth h_S are the same. For the same model, the larger the standard deviation for the same average value of h_S , the larger the value of the load factors. Since the value of snow load $A_{node} \cdot \rho_S h_{S(n)}$ per node varies greatly depending on the average value of h_S from Table 4, it is difficult to compare the values of γ_S between cases with different average values of h_S . Therefore, we will analyze the relationship with β by converting to snow depth. In an excerpt, the relationship between $\gamma_S \cdot \rho_S h_{S(n)}/\rho_{S(1m)}$ and β for $\lambda=60, \sigma(h_S)=0.2m$, and $\mu(h_S)=0.3, 0.5, 1.0$, and $2.0m$ is shown in Fig. 9. $\rho_{S(1m)}$ is the unit weight of snow when $h_S=1.0m$.

Fig. 8: The results of reliability analyses ($\lambda=60, \mu(h_S)=0.5m$)

Fig. 9: The relationships between reliability index β and $\gamma_S \cdot \rho_S h_{S(n)}/\rho_{S(1m)}$

For example, if $\beta=3.0$ is targeted when $w_{i0}/t_{eq}=0.0$, it can be seen that a snow depth of about 1.3m must be assumed regardless of the model in areas when $\mu(h_S)=0.5$ and $\sigma(h_S)=0.2m$. In addition, since the coefficient of variation at locations with small average values, such as $\mu(h_S)=0.3m$, is large, it may be necessary to assume a relatively large snow depth, approximately 2.8m at $\beta=4.0$, according to Fig. 9. Therefore, from Fig. 6, these are areas where the coefficient of variation of $v(h_S)$ is as large as 0.8

in general areas, and if h_S is assumed to follow a lognormal distribution in such areas, it may be on the dangerous side to determine the snow depth to be used for design based on the average value alone.

7. Conclusion

Reliability analyses were conducted for cylindrical lattice shell roofs subjected to uniform distributed snow loads, assuming that the snow depth follows a log-normal distribution for a 100-year return period, with average values and standard deviations for roof-only models and models with substructures. It is concluded as follows, from the above results.

- 1) When the probability characteristics of h_S are the same, the value of the load factor required to satisfy a given β is larger as the member slenderness ratio is larger and the substructure stiffness is smaller.
- 2) The larger the standard deviation, the larger the demanded load factor for the same model, when the average value of h_S is the same.
- 3) Even if the standard deviations of h_S are equal, the coefficient of variation increases when the average value is small, so a relatively large snow depth may be required when β is large.

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